

Design example of a composite road bridge

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ABSTRACT

Fibre-reinforced polymer composite is a competitive material for traffic bridges and decks due to low self-weight, significant fatigue life and corrosion resistance compared to steel and reinforced concrete. Composite decks are commercially available as stand-alone short-span bridges or as decks on primary girders, with or without composite action. The Technical Specification for Design of fibre-polymer composite structures (CEN/TS19101: 2022; TS) provides holistic design guidance for composite bridges. This paper presents the application of the design rules and verification analysis according to TS on a 7,35 m single span stand-alone regional road bridge, with load models according to prEN1991-2. The bridge section is vacuum infused web-core sandwich with multi-directional glass fibre laminates. ULS, SLS, fatigue and creep deformation are verified with partial factors for material, resistance models and conversion factors according to TS. A FE model of the whole bridge deck is built using shell elements for facings and webs to account for their interaction in global and local (wheel load) analysis, multi-axial stress states and local buckling. The study demonstrates the simple and more advanced analysis in line with the Eurocode and TS and highlights areas where optimizations are needed.

KEYWORDS

FRP materials and products; All FRP structures; FRP bridge; Code and design guidelines; Case studies and applications

INTRODUCTION AND DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

This example demonstrates the procedures as described in the Technical Specification for Design of fibre-polymer composite structures CEN/TS 19101:2022, further referred to as TS. Selected exemplar Serviceability Limit State (SLS) and Ultimate Limit State (ULS) verifications are performed on the critical aspects for a glass fibre reinforced polyester traffic web-core sandwich deck of a road bridge, produced with a standard vacuum infusion method. Design requirements are considered as for a regional traffic road bridge designed for LM1 and LM2 loads, in combination with the distributed traffic loads according to prEN1991-2:2021. The bridge has a design service life of 100 years, is of consequence class CC2 (prEN1990:2021) and fatigue traffic class 3 (prEN1991-2), i.e. number of passing heavy vehicles per year $N_{obs} = 125.000$. The bridge has 2 lanes and the length and the span of the bridge is $L = 7,35$ m. For the purpose of this design example, the bridge structure was simplified to a single lane rectangular composite road deck panel, $B = 3,026$ m wide, supported at the ends with simple line supports one of which is released in the longitudinal direction.

BRIDGE LAYOUT

The structural concept (cross-section) of the bridge can be considered a web-core sandwich structure with total depth of 430 mm. Details of the deck's schematic cross section are shown in Figure 1. It consists of top face sheet and bottom face sheet, each $t_f=25,7$ mm thick, as multi-directional laminate connected by longitudinal webs with centre-to-centre distance $b_w=104,1$ mm and $t_w=6,9$ mm thickness that are made of quasi-isotropic laminate. Connection between the webs and the face sheets is accomplished by continuation of the plies from webs to the face sheets. Longitudinal webs are connected by $t_{wtw}=2,1$ mm thin transverse webs at center-to-center distance of $b_{wtw} = 70$ mm in the top

250 mm part of the panel to improve local stability of the face sheets and longitudinal webs. Non-structural foam blocks between the face sheets and webs are facilitated in the production process and embedded mould.

Figure 1 – Layout and parameters of the web-core sandwich panel cross section

E-glass fibre reinforcement and unsaturated polyester resin are used to produce the bridge in a vacuum infusion process. It has been built by wrapping dry glass fibre fabrics around non-structural foam core blocks, as well as additional fabrics stacked on top and below, integrated and alternating with the core blocks. The bridge deck structure is fully produced in a single resin infusion step. On top a bauxite-epoxy wear surface with a thickness of 6 mm is applied. The ply stack of the facings and webs are of a symmetric and balanced lay-up. The top and bottom face sheets are built as GC75 (glass-composite 75% UD dominated): $[0/90/0/0]_{14s}$ with 75% of the fibre reinforcement in the x-direction of the laminate (longitudinal direction of the bridge) and 25% in the y-direction. Fibre volume fraction in the face sheets is $V_f = 52\%$ and density 1880 kg/m^3 . The longitudinal and transverse webs are built as GCQI (glass-composite quasi-isotropic): $[0/90/45/-45]_{2s}$, with 25% of the fibre reinforcement in the x-direction, 25% in the y-direction and 25% at an angle of 45° and -45° with respect to the x-axis of the laminate, respectively. Fibre volume fraction in the webs is $V_f = 28\%$ and density 1564 kg/m^3 .

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Material tests have been performed on 5 to 10 sub-laminate samples for the GC75 material and for the GCQI material. The samples are manufactured using the same constituent materials and same resin infusion process used to produce the bridge deck. The results relevant for this example are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 as mean values X_m and coefficient of variation V_x on basis of number of specimens n . X and y denote the in-plane longitudinal and transverse directions, and z the out-of-plane direction.

Table 1 – Material properties of face sheet laminate GC75 $[0/90/0/0]_{14s}$, $V_f = 52\%$

Property	Abbreviation	Test standard	n [-]	X_m [MPa]	V_x [%]
Tensile strength x-direction	$f_{x,t}$	EN-ISO 527	6	738	4,90
Tensile strength y-direction	$f_{y,t}$	EN-ISO 527	6	314	5,60
Compressive strength x-direction	$f_{x,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	5	-447	5,00
Compressive strength y-direction	$f_{y,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	7	-221	4,90
In-plane shear strength	$f_{xy,v}$	ASTM D5379-D5379M	6	46	1,71
Tensile modulus x-direction	$E_{x,t}$	EN-ISO 527	5	33832	1,70
Tensile modulus y-direction	$E_{y,t}$	EN-ISO 527	6	16042	5,00
Compressive modulus x-direction	$E_{x,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	5	36619	2,30
Compressive modulus y-direction	$E_{y,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	7	20731	6,30

Table 2 – Material properties of web laminate GCQI $[0/90/45/-45]_{2s}$, $V_f = 28\%$

Property	Abbreviation	Test standard	n [-]	X_m [MPa]	V_x [%]
Tensile strength x-direction	$f_{x,t}$	EN-ISO 527	7	177	7,78
Tensile strength y-direction	$f_{y,t}$	EN-ISO 527	10	177	7,14
Compressive strength x-direction	$f_{x,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	5	207	7,15
Compressive strength y-direction	$f_{y,c}$	EN-ISO 14126	7	183	6,13
In-plane shear strength	$f_{xy,v}$	ASTM D5379-D5379M	6	179	3,29
Tensile modulus x-direction	$E_{x,t}$	EN-ISO 527	7	11405	2,50
Tensile modulus y-direction	$E_{y,t}$	EN-ISO 527	10	11199	2,40
Shear modulus xy-direction	G_{xy}	ASTM D5379	6	4398	2,50

DESIGN VALUES OF RESISTANCE

The design values of resistance X_d for the different material properties of the laminates are calculated on the basis of determining the characteristic values of properties X_k , partial factors for the resistance model γ_{Rd} and for the material γ_m and conversion the factor η_c defined in Eq.1 from TS. Conversion factor is considered for reduction of each material property separately (stiffness or strength) as combination of short-term impact of temperature η_{ct} and long-term influence of moisture exposure η_{cm} according to Eq. 2. Calculation of the design value of the representative properties is shown in Table 3 and Table 4 for the laminates to the face sheets and webs, respectively. Major steps and procedure of determining the governing parameters shown in Table 3 and Table 4 are explained here further.

$$X_d = \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd}} \cdot \left(\eta_c \cdot \frac{X_k}{\gamma_m} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\eta_c = \eta_{ct} \cdot \eta_{cm}, \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The characteristic value X_k is determined as 5% fractile on the basis of the mean property value X_m , coefficient of variation V_x and number of tested specimens according to Eq. 3 from prEN1990, Annex C (Equation (C.15)), for the calculation of the characteristic value of lognormal distributed variables. This choice is consistent with the determination of the values of the partial factor for the material γ_m for which a lognormal distribution is also assumed according to TS.

$$X_k = X_m \cdot \exp \left\{ -k_n \cdot \sqrt{\ln(1 + V_x^2)} - \frac{\ln(1 + V_x^2)}{2} \right\}, \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The partial factor for the resistance model is $\gamma_{Rd} = 1,4$ for the material failure and $\gamma_{Rd} = 1,3$ for local buckling are taken according to TS. The partial factor for the material γ_m is determined on the basis of value of the known and/or the corrected coefficient of variation V_x , according to Table 4.1 in TS. The minimum and the maximum values of γ_m are 1,07 and 1,82, corresponding to values of the coefficient of variation V_x of 0,05 and 0,45, respectively. In determination of partial factor for the material the TS the accounts for the statistical uncertainty in the coefficient of variation V_x by increasing the coefficient of variation determined in the coupon experiments $V_{x,exp}$ by a factor f_{V_x} . The correction factor is defined in TS on the basis of number of the specimens tested. However, in this example the supplier of the bridge has built a large number of bridge decks with the same materials, structure and production technique as applied in this example. Material tests are regularly performed as part of the quality control and collected in a company database. The coefficient of variation V_x , is considered to be known hence the factor f_{V_x} does not apply, i.e. $V_x = V_{x,exp}$. In case of face sheets material tests are performed on a sublaminates level, i.e. the same materials with the same fibre orientation, but with a thickness of 3,4 mm. According to TS in such cases an additional factor of 1,2 is required for determining the design resistance of the laminate. Hence, two values for partial factor for the material γ_m are shown in Table 3, with values in brackets being the uncorrected values. Values of the the elastic properties are used without correction.

Table 3 – Design values of resistance face sheet material G75 [0/90/0/0]_{2s}, $V_f = 52\%$.

Property	n [-]	X_m [MPa]	$V_{x,exp}$ [%]	X_k [MPa]	V_x [%]	γ_m [-]	γ_{Rd} [-]	η_c [-]	X_d [MPa]
$f_{x,t}$	6	738	4,90	674	4,90	1,28 (1,07)	1,40	0,71	264
$f_{y,t}$	6	314	5,60	283	5,60	1,3 (1,08)	1,40	0,71	110
$f_{x,c}$	5	-447	5,00	-407	5,00	1,28 (1,07)	1,40	0,39	-87
$f_{y,c}$	7	-221	4,90	-202	4,90	1,28 (1,07)	1,40	0,39	-42
$f_{xy,v}$	6	46	1,71	45	1,71	1,28 (1,07)	1,40	0,71	17
$E_{x,t}$	5	33832	1,70	32797	1,70	-	-	-	-
$E_{y,t}$	6	16042	5,00	14623	5,00	-	-	-	-
$E_{x,c}$	5	36619	2,30	35103	2,30	1,07	1,30	0,71	-
$E_{y,c}$	7	20731	6,30	18446	6,30	1,09	1,30	0,71	-
G_{xy}	6	4201	3,75	3922	3,75	1,07	1,30	0,71	-

Table 4 – Design values of resistance web material GQI [0/90/45/-45]_{2s}, V_f = 28%.

Property	<i>n</i> [-]	<i>X_m</i> [MPa]	<i>V_{x,exp}</i> [%]	<i>X_k</i> [MPa]	<i>V_x</i> [%]	<i>γ_m</i> [-]	<i>γ_{Rd}</i> [-]	<i>η_c</i> [-]	<i>X_d</i> [MPa]
<i>f_{x,t}</i>	7	177	7,78	153	7,78	1,11	1,40	0,71	69
<i>f_{y,t}</i>	10	177	7,14	155	7,14	1,10	1,40	0,71	71
<i>f_{x,c}</i>	5	-207	7,15	180	7,15	1,10	1,40	0,39	-45
<i>f_{y,c}</i>	7	-183	6,13	163	6,13	1,10	1,40	0,39	-40
<i>f_{xy,v}</i>	6	179	5,76	169	5,76	1,10	1,40	0,71	77
<i>E_{x,t}</i>	7	11405	2,50	10906	2,50	1,07	-	0,71	-
<i>E_{y,t}</i>	10	11199	2,40	10737	2,40	1,07	-	0,71	-
<i>G_{xy}</i>	6	4398	2,50	4204	2,50	1,07	-	0,71	-

Mean elastic properties are required for modelling the deflections of the structure to verify SLS. However, elastic properties are also used in determination of the resistance to local buckling and creep rupture as ULS verification, hence for the elastic properties the partial factor and the conversion factors are also shown in Table 3 and Table 4. According to TS the calculation of the conversion factor for temperature effects considers the relation between the service temperature T_s and the glass transition temperature of the material T_g . In absence of a more specific procedure defined in the Eurocode, the maximum service temperature $T_s = 68^\circ\text{C}$ is calculated on the basis of EN 1991-1-5, figure 6.1, assuming that the most applicable is the thermal model for steel structures of Type I. The glass transition temperature (onset) of the unsaturated polyester resin that is used in the example is $T_g = 90^\circ\text{C}$ which fulfils the requirement of the TS that the T_g is at least 20°C higher than T_s . Different conversion factors for temperature are used for fibre-dominated Eq. 4 and matrix-dominated Eq. 5 material properties.

$$\eta_{ct} = \min\left\{1,0 - 0,25 \cdot \frac{T_s - 20}{T_g - 20}; 1,0\right\} = 1,0 - 0,25 \cdot \frac{68 - 20}{90 - 20} = 0,83 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\eta_{ct} = \min\left\{1,0 - 0,80 \cdot \frac{T_s - 20}{T_g - 20}; 1,0\right\} = 1,0 - 0,80 \cdot \frac{68 - 20}{90 - 20} = 0,45 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The exposure class is important for defining the reduction of material properties due to moisture effects. Exposure class II is used in the presented example (bridge outdoors) with wet/dry conditions resulting in conversion factor for moisture of $\eta_{cm} = 0,85$. The total conversion factors are shown in Eq. 6 and 7. The face sheet laminate has 75% of the fibres in the 0° -direction and 25% fibre reinforcement in 90° -direction. The web laminate is quasi-isotropic with 25% of the fibres in each direction. Therefore, for the face sheet and for the web laminates all tensile properties and in-plane shear strength of the web are considered fibre-dominated. All compressive properties of the face sheet and the web and the in-plane shear strength of the face sheet are considered matrix-dominated, according to TS.

$$\eta_c = \eta_{ct} \cdot \eta_{cm} = 0,83 \cdot 0,85 = 0,71, \text{ for fibre-dominated properties} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\eta_c = \eta_{ct} \cdot \eta_{cm} = 0,45 \cdot 0,85 = 0,39, \text{ for matrix-dominated properties} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

LOADS AND ACTIONS

Self-weight of the bridge cross section is 146 kg/m^2 including top and bottom face sheets, longitudinal and transverse webs. Adding $14,4 \text{ kg/m}^2$ weight of the foam core results in $1,57 \text{ kN/m}^2$ of permanent load. Additional permanent load consists of $0,15 \text{ kN/m}^2$ of epoxy-bauxite surfacing and weight of the accessories (parapets and guardrails) averaged to a smeared load of $1,0 \text{ kN/m}^2$.

For ULS, SLS and creep rupture verifications, the variable loads due to traffic were considered using two load models: LM1 (global) and LM2 (local) according to prEN1991-2 with all load correction factors for distributed and wheel loads being equal to $\alpha_{Qi} = \alpha_{qi} = 1,0$. Vertical loads due to LM1 consisted of heaviest double axle Tandem System (TS) with axle load $Q_{1k} = 300 \text{ kN}$ (per axle) and Uniformly Distributed Load (UDL) in the heavy lane $q_{1k} = 9 \text{ kN/m}^2$. Alternatively, the load model LM2 considers one heavy axle load (two wheels) of $Q_{ak} = 400 \text{ kN}$. Corresponding horizontal traffic loads

according to prEN1991-2, not detailed here, were considered to act simultaneously with the vertical traffic loads.

For FLS verifications load models FLM1 is considered. The load model FLM1 is an equivalent constant amplitude load model based on LM1 defined by 70% and 30% of the TS and ULD, respectively, therefore, $Q_{1k} = 210$ kN (per axle) and $q_{1k} = 2,7$ kN/m². The wheel print of FLM1 is 400×400mm². Load combinations considered in the analyses conform NEN-EN-1990; National Annex table NB 19. Values of $\gamma_F = 1,2$ for permanent loads and $\gamma_F = 1,35$ for traffic loads are accounting for consequence class CC2 in accordance with prEN1991-2 in ULS combinations. Load factors are not considered for SLS verifications. The total factor applied is the resultant from the load factor multiplied with combination factor ψ_1 which equals 1,0 for ULS except for the horizontal loads where $\psi_1 = 0,8$. In SLS verifications frequent load situation according to NEN-EN1990 is considered resulting in combination factor $\psi_1 = 0,8$ for the traffic load. With the stated factors two simplified ULS combinations are defined according to eq. 6.10b from prEN1990:

$$ULS-1: 1,2 \times \text{Permanent Loads} + 1,35 \times LM1_TS + 1,35 \times LM1_UDL + 0,8 \times 1,35 \text{ Horizontal Traffic Load}$$

$$ULS-2: 1,2 \times \text{Permanent Loads} + 1,35 \times LM2_TS$$

The wheel loads for the tandem systems LM1_TS and LM2_TS are modelled as areas with uniform pressure of 937,5 kN/m² and 952 kN/m² on contact area of 400×400 mm² and 600×350 mm², respectively. For both load models two locations have been considered: midspan (for maximum deflection and bending moment) and near the support, for maximum shear force.

NUMERICAL MODELS

The analysis of the bridge is done by finite element (FE)-modelling in software RFEM version 5.21. Linear elastic shell elements are used to model the laminates of the face sheets and webs with homogenized orthotropic properties (mean values) as defined in Table 3 and Table 4. For the webs 8 square shaped elements are used along the height, and for the face sheets 2 elements between the longitudinal webs. Transverse webs aren't included for simplicity of the FE model. Details of the model are presented in Figure 2. The deck is simply supported by two line supports at each end of the deck one side being released to translate in longitudinal direction. On the other end, only the translations in Y- and Z-direction are fixed. All rotations are free. The local axes per structural element can be also seen in the figures. The model is validated by comparing the reaction forces and the deflections under permanent load ($1,75 + 0,15 = 1,72$ kN/m²) to the analytical calculation. In both numerical and analytical calculation 0,95 mm vertical deflection in the middle of the span is obtained, see Figure 6b.

Figure 2 – Details of the shell element based FE model of the bridge in RFEM software

DESIGN VERIFICATIONS

From the FE-analysis it was seen that ULS-1 load combination resulted in slightly higher shear stresses in the webs than the ULS-2. All governing stresses are therefore in this (simplified) example related to load combination ULS-1. In the figures below, the maximum occurring stresses in the structural elements are presented. Results relevant for the top face sheet are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4, while results relevant for the longitudinal webs are presented in Figure 5. Results of the bottom face sheet and the vertical transverse end plates over the supports are calculated and verified but not shown

in this paper. All stresses are reported in the local coordinate system. Normal stresses are positive in tension and negative in compression. The transverse webs are not included in the model, resulting in slightly higher stresses in the face sheets and the longitudinal webs. The longitudinal normal stresses (x-direction) and in-plane shear stresses in face sheets and the webs are mostly the result of membrane behaviour. Therefore, the variability of longitudinal stresses through the thickness is small and results are presented from the middle of the laminates being representative as well for the element's top and bottom surface. In the transverse direction the effect of local bending of the face sheets around the webs is significant therefore the y-direction stresses in the face sheets are given in the element's top and bottom surface. Final ULS verifications are done by combination of stresses at element's top and bottom surface.

a) Longitudinal (x-direction) normal stress b) Shear stresses
 Figure 3 – Maximum design values of in-plane stresses in the top face sheet (middle of laminate)

a) Top of the face sheet b) Bottom of the face sheet
 Figure 4 – Maximum design values of transverse (y-direction) stresses in the top face sheet

a) Longitudinal (x-direction) normal stress b) Vertical (y-direction) normal stress

c) Shear stresses (load near the support)

Figure 5 – Maximum design values of in-plane stresses in the longitudinal webs (middle of laminate)

ULS - Individual stress components

TS provides rules to verify material failure on the level of laminate or in a more detailed analysis on the ply level. In this example the verification is done on the laminate level because the material properties (resistances) are also determined on the laminate level. As a first check the stresses are verified individually, considering only uni-axial stress states. In a next step the combined stress states will be verified. Design action effects as stresses from FE model shown in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 for the top face sheet and the longitudinal webs are compared to design values of resistances from Table 3 and Table 4, respectively and the ratios are shown in Table 5 and Table 6. For all individual stress components the design action effects (stresses) satisfy the design values of resistances.

Table 5 – Design verification of individual stress components - top face sheet

Failure mode	Design action effects (E_d)	Design Value Resistance (R_d)	E_d/R_d
Tensile failure x-direction	$(\sigma_{x,t,Ed})_f = 9,9$ MPa	$(f_{x,t,d})_f = 264$ MPa	0,04
Compression failure x-direction	$(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_f = -69,9$ MPa	$(f_{x,c,d})_f = -87$ MPa	0,80
Tensile failure y-direction	$(\sigma_{y,t,Ed})_f = 34,3$ MPa	$(f_{y,t,d})_f = 132$ MPa	0,26
Compression failure y-direction	$(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_f = -33,5$ MPa	$(f_{y,c,d})_f = -42$ MPa	0,80
Shear failure	$(\tau_{xy,Ed})_f = 7,9$ MPa	$(f_{xy,d})_f = 17$ MPa	0,46

Table 6 – Design verification of individual stress components - longitudinal webs

Failure mode	Design action effects (E_d)	Design Value Resistance (R_d)	E_d/R_d
Tensile failure x-direction	$(\sigma_{x,t,Ed})_w = 22,7$ MPa	$(f_{x,t,d})_w = 69$ MPa	0,33
Compression failure x-direction	$(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_w = -26,8$ MPa	$(f_{x,c,d})_w = -43$ MPa	0,60
Tensile failure y-direction	$(\sigma_{y,t,Ed})_w = 21$ MPa	$(f_{y,t,d})_w = 71$ MPa	0,30
Compression failure y-direction	$(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_w = -27,7$ MPa	$(f_{y,c,d})_w = -41$ MPa	0,70
Shear failure	$(\tau_{xy,Ed})_w = 26$ MPa	$(f_{xy,c,d})_w = 77$ MPa	0,34

ULS - Combined (multi-axial) stress state

For regions with a complex stress state with combined stresses, a detailed analysis shall be performed in accordance with TS, to include the effect of stress interactions. Verification is performed here based on the most simplistic, laminate level, analysis which according to TS assumes linear summation of utilisation of individual stress components at a critical point in laminate. The combined stress verification needs to be performed for all locations with simultaneously occurring (high) multi-axial stresses. This occurs in regions such as supports and under wheel print loads. As an example, the combined stresses are verified for the top face sheet and the longitudinal webs. Individual stress components and related utilisations are already shown in Table 5 and Table 6 for the top face sheet and the longitudinal webs. The locations of maximum individual stresses are coinciding and are related to the same location of the load, thus simultaneous. For the top face sheet and the longitudinal webs the combined stress criteria are calculated in Eq. 8 and Eq. 9, respectively. In principle the locations with compressive stresses are critical in this example due to more severe reduction of the compressive strength of the laminates by the conversion factor for temperature (matrix-dominated). The values of shear stresses are obtained in the FE model at the location of maximum normal stresses, thus lower than the ones presented in tables where extreme shear stresses were used for verifying the individual stress components.

$$\frac{(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{x,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{y,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\tau_{xy,Ed})_f}{(f_{xy,d})_f} = \frac{-69,9}{-87} + \frac{-33,5}{-47} + \frac{5}{17} = 0,8 + 0,8 + 0,29 = 1,89 \leq 1 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\frac{(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_w}{(f_{x,c,d})_w} + \frac{(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_w}{(f_{y,c,d})_w} + \frac{(\tau_{xy,Ed})_w}{(f_{xy,d})_w} = \frac{-27}{-45} + \frac{-28}{-40} + \frac{9}{77} = 0,6 + 0,7 + 0,12 = 1,42 \leq 1 \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

For both the top face sheet and the webs the combined stress criterion is not fulfilled. An option would be to perform ply level analysis with progressive failure analysis which is possible according to TS. In this example another approach is used. It is seen that especially high stresses occur in the y-direction (transverse) of the top face sheet. Thus, further verification of the combined stress state is still done on the laminate level, using linear summation as interaction criterion but with a more detailed FE-model, including the transverse webs and mesh refinement. As expected, inclusion of the transverse webs largely reduced the stresses in the transverse (y-direction) of the face sheet from $-33,5 \text{ N/mm}^2$ to $-7,8 \text{ N/mm}^2$, by preventing its local bending due to local wheel loads. In addition, the longitudinal normal stress (x-direction) in the top face sheet is reduced from $-69,9 \text{ N/mm}^2$ to $-59,9 \text{ N/mm}^2$ as consequence of engaging larger number of longitudinal webs in the transfer of the local wheel loads. Using refined mesh led to more accurate determination of shear stresses in the top face sheet at the location of extreme normal stresses. The corresponding value of the shear stress reduced from the value of 5 N/mm^2 in the initial model (without the transverse webs) to the value of $0,42 \text{ N/mm}^2$ in the model with transverse webs and refined mesh. Similar reductions of local individual stress components are found in webs as well. The verification of combined stress is fulfilled with stresses obtained from the refined FE model both for the top face sheet and the longitudinal webs, as shown in Eq. 10 and Eq. 11, respectively.

$$\frac{(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{x,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{y,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\tau_{xy,Ed})_f}{(f_{xy,d})_f} = \frac{-59,9}{-87} + \frac{-7,8}{-47} + \frac{0,42}{17} = 0,69 + 0,17 + 0,02 = 0,89 < 1 \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\frac{(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{x,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_f}{(f_{y,c,d})_f} + \frac{(\tau_{xy,Ed})_f}{(f_{xy,d})_f} = \frac{-20,7}{-45} + \frac{-16,3}{-40} + \frac{2,19}{77} = 0,46 + 0,41 + 0,03 = 0,9 < 1 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Local effects of wheel print and surfacing layer

Additional analyses were made with detailed FE model to check local multi-axial stress state in case the wheel prints smaller than $400 \times 400 \text{ mm}^2$ would be applied. The same local wheel load originating from LM1 (150 kN per wheel) has been used on a reduced wheel print area corresponding to the smallest wheel print given in prEN1991-2 - the wheel A ($320 \text{ mm} \times 220 \text{ mm}$). Motive for using such high wheel loads is continuously increasing traffic demands. In practice overloading is possible and existing. For example TNO in the Netherlands measured axle loads up to 250 kN in period of 2013. Note that the analysed situation does not represent a required Eurocode prescribed design check, at the time of writing of this Example, but is performed to show how sensitive local stresses can be to a combination of wheel print and surfacing thickness on a composite deck. The analysis is done with variation of thickness of the surface layer from 6 mm, the one used in this example utilising thin epoxy-bauxite surfacing, up to 75 mm which is established for asphalt surfacing on bridges. Results revealed that E_d/R_d for local multi-axial stresses reached 1,35 in case of the small wheel print. The surfacing layer of 75 mm thickness spreads the load to an effective area of $450 \times 370 \text{ mm}^2$ leading to $E_d/R_d = 1,0$ obtained by stresses from the refined FE model. Overall, 35% reduction of the local multi-axial stress magnitude is achieved by increasing the surfacing layer thickness from 6 mm to 75 mm.

ULS - Local buckling

Verification of local buckling of the face sheets and longitudinal webs is done with design value of action (stresses) obtained in the simplified FE model shown in Figure 2. The resistance to local buckling is calculated following the clauses of TS. The resistance to buckling is based on critical buckling stress for the representative geometry (thickness and width), boundary conditions on the longitudinal edges (free, simply supported, clamped) and type of loading (uniform compression, linearly distribution due to in-plane bending or in-plane shear). Alternatively critical stresses can be obtained using an FE analysis. Two local buckling failure modes in the top face sheet are verified. First is local buckling due to uniform compression in longitudinal x-direction that is result of global bending of the bridge with traffic load in the middle of the span. Transverse interaction between the strips of the bridge that are loaded by local load and the strips to the bridge to the left and to the right of the loaded region can lead to global transverse bending of the bridge cross section resulting in compressive transverse stress in the top face sheet and tensile membrane stresses in the bottom face sheet. This failure mode is also verified.

Three local buckling failure modes are considered in the longitudinal webs. The first failure mode is due to a linearly distributed compression in the longitudinal x-direction due to global bending of the bridge with local traffic load in the middle of the span. The second failure mode is buckling in the vertical direction under the local wheel print load resulting in uniform compression in transverse y-direction. The third failure mode is buckling due to in-plane shear in the web with local traffic load located near the supports. An example of such calculation is presented for buckling of the longitudinal web due to linearly distributed compression stresses in longitudinal x-direction. Final results of other failure modes are presented in Table 7 and Table 8 for the face sheets and the longitudinal webs, respectively. Information on most relevant input parameters used in the calculation is included: width of the laminate and boundary conditions along the longitudinal edges of the “long” plate. The calculation used in this example makes use of formulas for local buckling given in TS, Annex C that are based on theory of buckling of long orthotropic plates. The formulas are based on flexural stiffnesses of the plate, i.e. “D” components of the ABD stiffness matrix from the classical laminate theory. In the present example the material properties are determined in the laminate level, not the ply level. Therefore, the formulas from TS that provide calculation of flexural stiffnesses of the orthotropic plate based on homogenized properties of the laminate are used. For the longitudinal webs considered in x-direction those are given by Eq. 12 to Eq. 15.

$$(D_{11})_{wx} = \frac{\eta_c \cdot (E_{x,c,k})_w \cdot t_w^3}{12 \cdot (1 - (v_{xy,k})_w \cdot (v_{yx,k})_w)} = \frac{0,71 \cdot 10906 \cdot 6,9^3}{12 \cdot (1 - 0,34 \cdot 0,34)} = 23,8 \cdot 10^4 \text{ N} \cdot \text{mm} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$(D_{22})_{wx} = \frac{\eta_c \cdot (E_{y,c,k})_w \cdot t_w^3}{12 \cdot (1 - (v_{yx,k})_w \cdot (v_{xy,k})_w)} = \frac{0,71 \cdot 10737 \cdot 6,9^3}{12 \cdot (1 - 0,34 \cdot 0,34)} = 23,4 \cdot 10^4 \text{ N} \cdot \text{mm} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$(D_{12})_{wx} = (v_{yx,k})_w \cdot (D_{11})_w = 0,34 \cdot 23,8 \cdot 10^4 = 8,09 \cdot 10^4 \text{ N} \cdot \text{mm} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$(D_{66})_{wx} = \frac{\eta_c \cdot (G_{xy,k})_w \cdot t_w^3}{12} = \frac{0,71 \cdot 4204 \cdot 6,9^3}{12} = 8,1 \cdot 10^4 \text{ N} \cdot \text{mm} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

In this case the buckling width equals the height of the longitudinal webs (c.t.c. between the face sheets), see Figure 1, i.e. $b = h_w = 430 - 25,7 = 404,3$ mm. The support of the webs by the face sheets is considered clamped (CL), due to the high bending stiffness of the face sheets, compared to the bending stiffness of the longitudinal webs. Based on the buckling constant K calculated in Eq. 16 which fulfils the criteria that $K < 3$ the Eq. 17 is selected based on TS to calculate the critical buckling stress for such loading and the boundary conditions.

$$K = \frac{2 \cdot (D_{66})_{wx} + (D_{12})_{wx}}{\sqrt{(D_{11})_{wx} \cdot (D_{22})_{wx}}} = 1,03 \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

$$(f_{x,b,cr,k})_w = \frac{\pi^2}{t_w \cdot b^2} \cdot [26,8 \cdot \sqrt{(D_{11})_{wx} \cdot (D_{22})_{wx}} + 12,9 \cdot ((D_{12})_{wx} + 2 \cdot (D_{66})_{wx})] = 82,7 \text{ MPa} \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

The material partial factor corresponds to $E_{x,c}$. Because $E_{x,c}$ is not measured in the test, the value based on $E_{x,t}$ is taken, equal to $\gamma_m = 1,07$, see

Table 4. The partial factor accounting for the uncertainty in the resistance model for local buckling is: $\gamma_{Rd} = 1,3$. The buckling reduction factor for compression in the x-direction to consider imperfections is $\chi_{y,c} = 1,0$ (for flat laminates), according to TS. The design value of the critical buckling compressive stress in the y-direction of the longitudinal web is given by:

$$(f_{y,cr,d})_w = \frac{1}{\gamma_m \cdot \gamma_{Rd}} \cdot \chi_{y,c} \cdot (f_{y,cr,k})_w = \frac{1}{1,07 \cdot 1,3} \cdot 1,0 \cdot 82,7 = 59,4 \text{ MPa} \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

Table 7 – Design verification of local buckling - top face sheet

Failure mode	Design action effects (E_d)	Width (b)	Boundary conditions	Design Value Resistance (R_d)	E_d/R_d
Uniform compression (x-direction)	$(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_f$ = -69,9 MPa	$b_w = 104,1$ mm	Simply supported at both ends	$(f_{x,cr,d})_f$ = -1829 MPa	0,04
Uniform compression (y-direction)	$(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_f$ = -33,5 MPa	$b_{wtw} = 70$ mm	Simply supported at both ends	$(f_{y,cr,d})_f$ = -1160 MPa	0,03

Table 8 – Design verification of local buckling - longitudinal webs

Failure mode	Design action effects (E_d)	Width (b)	Boundary conditions	Design Value Resistance (R_d)	E_d/R_d
Linear distributed (x-direction)	$(\sigma_{x,c,Ed})_w = -27 \text{ MPa}$	$h_w = 404,3 \text{ mm}$	Clamped at both ends	$(f_{x,b,cr,d})_w = -59,4 \text{ MPa}$	0,45
Uniform compression (y-direction)	$(\sigma_{y,c,Ed})_w = -28 \text{ MPa}$	$b_{wtw} = 70 \text{ mm}$	Simply supported at both ends	$(f_{y,cr,d})_w = -200 \text{ MPa}$	0,14
In-plane shear	$(\tau_{xy,Ed})_w = 26 \text{ MPa}$	200 mm	Simply supported at both ends	$(f_{xy,cr,d})_w = 32,7 \text{ MPa}$	0,80

SLS - Deflections including creep

In this example project, due to the short span of the bridge, it is assumed that the agreement is made with the Bridge Owner that the serviceability limit should be verified under frequent load combination value of traffic load tandem system, excluding the effect of creep. The effect of creep is compensated for in the initial shape of the bridge. The deflection criterion is meant to verify the stiffness of the bridge. Deflections under traffic load and permanent load due to self-weight of the bridge are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Deflections of the bridge calculated by FE model (without conversion factors)

The SLS- load was specified as $\psi_1 \cdot \text{LM1_TS}$, in which the factor $\psi_1 = 0.8$ is a factor related to frequent load situation (Table A.2.1, National Annex of NEN-EN1990). The calculation of deflection shall include the conversion factor, with $\eta_c = 0,71$. As a conservative assumption the conversion factor is applied for the whole bridge cross section. Based on the average deflection in the mid of the span of 25 mm calculated in FE model for traffic load (see Figure 6a), the deflection to be considered as SLS-deflection under frequent load situation is 28 mm, see Eq. 19. Such deflection exceeds by 10% the established limit for such short bridges: $L/300 = 25 \text{ mm}$. Please note that the application of the conversion factor is very conservative. Only to the top surface is exposed to the highest temperature. Furthermore, the webs are protected from moisture ingress. More detailed distribution of the conversion factor can be considered by explicitly applying variable reduced material properties through the thickness of the bridge in the FE-model.

$$\Psi_1 \cdot w_{\text{LM1_TS}} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_c} = 0,8 \cdot 25 \cdot \frac{1}{0,71} = 28 \text{ mm} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

Permanent deformations including creep effects are calculated to determine the required minimal initial curvature of the deck that is needed to avoid sagging. Sagging of the deck is not allowed to prevent water ponding and for aesthetical reasons. Applying an initial curvature is a common solution for bridge decks produced with vacuum infusion technology. In addition to self-weight of the bridge of $1,72 \text{ kN/m}^2$, the additional weight of accessories (parapets and guardrails) of $1,0 \text{ kN/m}^2$ is considered in the permanent loads to calculate creep deformation. The initial deformation due to permanent loads, excluding creep effects, can be determined from FE model results presented in Figure 6b by factoring to include the additional weight of the accessories which becomes: $0,95 \cdot (1,72+1,0)/1,0 = 1,5 \text{ mm}$. In order to include creep effects the deformation due to bending and due to shear need to be separately

analysed because of different creep coefficients for the face sheet and web laminates. The main contribution to the resistance against bending deformation comes from the face sheets. The lay-up consists of 75% 0° fibres and 25% 90°fibres. As a conservative assumption, the creep coefficient defined in TS for balanced – woven bi-directional laminates is used (i.e. 50% 0°, 50% 90°fibres). For $t = 100$ years then $\phi_{E_{x,t}}(t = 100 \text{ years}) = 0,73$. The main contribution to the resistance against shear deformation comes from the webs, that have a quasi-isotropic lay-up, with a V_f of 28%. In absence of a more precise definition of the creep factor for such laminate with such low fibre volume fraction in TS, as a conservative assumption the value for G_{xz} of a UD-laminate is taken; $\phi_{G_{xy}}(t = 100 \text{ years}) = 2,94$. With bending stiffness of the entire bridge cross section $EI = 223,990 \text{ kNm}^2$ and a shear stiffness of $G_{xy} \cdot h_w \cdot t_w \cdot n_w = 438,38 \text{ kN}$, the resulting deformation including creep for the bridge deck plus wear surface is very small, only 3 mm, see Eq. 20. For practical reasons and to avoid water ponding, the initial curvature of the deck during manufacturing is set to an upward precamber of $L/200 = 35 \text{ mm}$.

$$d_{\text{fin}(t=100),\text{bridgedeck}} = \frac{5}{384} \cdot \frac{2,72 \cdot b_{\text{deck}} \cdot L^4}{EI} \cdot (1 + \phi_{E_{x,t}}(100)) + \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{2,72 \cdot b_{\text{deck}} \cdot L^2}{G_{xy} \cdot h_w \cdot t_w \cdot n_w} \cdot (1 + \phi_{G_{xz,t}}(100)) = 1,34 \cdot 1,73 + 0,16 \cdot 3,94 = 2,9 \text{ mm} \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

Fatigue resistance

The TS standard mandates the performance of fatigue verification for a structural member or joint if Eq. 21 is satisfied. In this case, Eq. 21 will be utilized to determine the need for a fatigue verification after calculating the bending moment and shear force on the bridge level. First, the bending moment action and resistance effect is calculated. Fatigue Load Model 1 (FLM1), where the The bending moment and shear force action effects are determined using FLM1. For the linear strain method, considering $\gamma_{Ff} = 1,0$ and $\Delta\phi_{\text{fat}} = 1,3$, the design action effect of the bending moment under FLM1 loading at midspan is calculated to be 911 kNm due to UDL of 2,7 kN/m² and tandem system of two axles 1,2 m apart, each 210 kN, at most unfavourable position in the spanwise direction. The bending moment resistance is determined per unit width using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. With a maximum allowable design stress in the face sheet of -87 MPa, the maximum allowable bending moment per meter width is determined to be 899,4 kNm (Eq. 22). Considering the presence of transverse webs and assuming no spread, the width of the structural element is taken equal to the width of the track of FLM1, i.e. 2 m. Consequently, the maximum allowable design bending moment is 1799 kNm.

$$\frac{E_d(\gamma_{Ff} Q_{\text{fat}})}{R_d} \geq 1,6 - 0,18 \cdot \lg(N) \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

$$(M_{y,Rd})_f = \frac{(f_{x,c})_f \cdot EI_{yy}}{(E_x)_f \cdot \frac{h}{2}} = \frac{87 \cdot 7,52 \cdot 10^{13}}{33832 \cdot \frac{430}{2}} = 899,4 \text{ kNm, per meter width.} \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

A similar approach is employed to determine the action and resistance effects for the shear force occurring in the longitudinal webs, not shown here. Finally, Eq. 21 is employed to analyze the fatigue bending moment. With the 125.000 of heavy vehicles per year, considering both axles of FLM1 as a separate load cycle, the total number of cycles over a 100-year time span is 25.000.000. Utilizing the derived values, in Eq. 23 it is determined that fatigue verification for the bending resistance is required. Verification can be performed by testing on component level according to specification of TS.

$$\frac{E_d(\gamma_{Ff} Q_{\text{fat}} \cdot \Delta\phi_{\text{fat}})}{R_d} = \frac{911 \text{ kNm}}{1799 \text{ kNm}} = 0,51 \geq 1,6 - 0,18 \cdot \lg(25.000.000) = 0,27 \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the presented study, an example of a design verification of a short span web-core composite bridge for road traffic is presented. Steps of ULS, SLS, buckling and fatigue checks are shown and calculations are performed following the specifications of TS. General conclusion is that the TS presents very comprehensive, coherent and complete set of rules and guidelines for desing of composite bridges. The following observations are made on the basis of the analyses performed and few potential points for

more detailed specification by future generation of the technical specification and/or national annexes are discussed:

- Multi-axial stress state in the top face sheet can be critical when conservative linear summation interaction criterion for laminate level analysis is used. Refined FE analysis incorporating additional elements, transverse webs in this example can help to verify the design. An alternative to reach more optimal design is to use more sophisticated calculation methods on ply level. TS opens for use of various failure theories and total or partial discount method for progressive failure analysis on ply level. Validation of a method to be used is responsibility of an engineer, therefore more verification cases would help in future to define more precise model factor in case detailed FE analysis is used.
- Buckling checks show to be more relevant for relatively thin webs in this example, compared to face sheets where critical stresses were found to be rather high (not critical).
- SLS verification relies on a good estimation of effect of temperature and creep. TS provides substantial information how to consider those effects for various situations used in this example for face sheet. More specification of creep factors for multi-directional laminates can be useful illustrated for instance by the need to adopt conservative estimates for the quasi-isotropic web laminate in this example.
- Developing dedicated service temperature distribution models through thickness of composite decks as addition to Eurocode's specification for steel and concrete, would be useful to better estimate deflections and strength under elevated temperatures which can be critical in the design verification.
- Creep rupture verification is required according to TS but is not shown here.
- A criterion for fatigue provided in TS based on number of cycles, ultimate static resistance and fatigue action indicates that detailed fatigue verification of the bridge deck in bending would be required. General fatigue load model from Eurocode is used. Developing mode dedicated equivalent fatigue load model for composite bridges could lead to more economical and reliable composite bridge designs.
- Thin-walled deck systems are sensitive to local peak stresses caused by local bending under wheel loads. Effective measures should be taken to avoid issues reported in the past for steel orthotropic decks and thin-walled composite decks. Peak stresses can be reduced for example by increasing the thickness of the surface layer, increasing the local thickness, introduction of transverse stiffeners, applying hard foam or balsa wood core material, etc.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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